

Mixed Ligand Complexes of bis(Ethylmalonato) Ni(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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Manuscript received 14 February 1977, accepted 27 April 1977

BETA-Diketones, esters, beta-keto esters and *o*-hydroxy carbonyl compounds have drawn considerable attention long since as oxygen donor-chelating ligands. We have been attempting¹⁻³ to prepare mixed ligand complexes with nitrogen and sulfur donors using metal chelates of these ligands. In this communication we report the mixed ligand complexes of heterocyclic amines and Ni(II) malonate.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. To an ethanolic solution of Ni(II) chloride, malonic ester was added in stoichiometric ratio and the solution shaken for fifteen minutes. Ammonia was added dropwise and the solution was allowed to stand over night when blue crystalline Ni(II) malonate separated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum.

Mixed ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing and ethanolic suspension of the chelate and amines in 1 : 2 ratio for about 2 hrs over water-bath. On cooling crystalline compounds separated out which were filtered/under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Metal was estimated complexometrically by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by standard microanalytical method. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the complexes by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made over solid specimen

at room temperature (25°) by Gouy method using Hg [Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. I.R. spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer-621 Spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 (chloroform-base) solution using HilgerWatt-U Vispock spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical and spectral data are recorded in Table-I.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the general formula : [NiL₂B₂] and [NiL₂B'] where L is malonic ester and B is a monodentate heterocyclic amine and B' is ethylenediamine. These are blue, green or light violet crystalline compounds, have fairly low melting points and soluble in acetone in which medium they behave as non-electrolytes the Δ_M being in the range of 8-15 mhos cm² μ_{eff} values range between 2.9 to 3.2 B.M. indicating the presence of two unpaired electrons and presumably a spin-free octahedral configuration.

Important infrared bands have been assigned. Ni(II) malonate has two absorption bands at 1600 and 1290 cm⁻¹ region attributable to ν(C=O) and ν(C-O) respectively. These two bands occur at a considerable lower frequency in the chelate compared to that of ethyl malonate, indicating bonding through oxygen. In the mixed ligand complexes these two bands are found ~1630 and ~1320 cm⁻¹ region, a shift to the high frequency side indicating bonding of the σ-bonded heterocyclic amines. Moreover, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands have been shifted in the complexes. Further bonding of the Ni(II) ion through the oxygen of the ester and nitrogen of the amines is confirmed by the observation of ν(M-C) and ν(M-N) ~ 510 and ~ 330 cm⁻¹ respectively in the far-infrared spectra.

In the electronic spectra of mixed ligand complexes three absorption bands appear around 10-11,

TABLE 1 ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY, I.R. SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) AND ELECTONIC SPCTRA K. K. (g)

Compound	% of Nickel Found Req'd.		% Nitrogen Found Req'd.		Δ mho Cm ²	μ _{eff} B.M.	ν(C=O)	ν(C-O)	ν(M-O)	ν(M-N)
[NiL ₂]	15.24	15.55	—	—	—	—	1600	1290	510	330
{NiL ₂ Py ₂ }	10.72	10.97	5.14	5.23	8.5	2.95	1620	1310	520	10(6),15(7), 24(16).
[NiL ₂ (γ-pic) ₂]	10.26	10.43	4.85	4.97	8.0	3.1	1610	1320	510	330 11.5(7), 15.8(7), 25(17).
[NiL ₂ (Pip) ₂]	10.58	10.73	4.96	5.12	11.6	3.05	1620	1315	520	325 11.6(6), 14.8(6), 14.5(15).
[NiL ₂ Q ₂]	8.83	9.08	4.47	4.56	10.4	3.1	1615	1310	530	320
[NiL ₂ (1.Q) ₂]	-8.89	9.08	4.45	4.56	14.3	3.2	1630	1320	530	320 11.5(7), 26(16), 15(6).
[NiL ₂ (2, 6-Lut) ₂]	9.77	9.93	4.62	4.74	15.0	3.0	1620	1315	510	320 10(6),14.5(5.5) 24.5(15).
[NiL ₂ en]	13.28	13.43	6.25	6.40	11.4	2.9	1610	1310	520	330 11.5(8), 17(7), 28(17).

L = Ethyl malonate, Py=Pyridine, γ-Pic= 4-Methyl pyridine, Pip=Piperidine, Q=Quinoline, 1.Q.=Isquinoline, 2, 6-Lut=2, 6-Lutidine, en=ethylenediamine.

15-17, and 24-28 K.K. region assignable⁴ to $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transition respectively. Extinction coefficient values are low in conformity with octahedral environment. Comparison of the bands with the solid state reflectance spectra of one representative compound indicates a little dissociation of the ligands in spite of the added base as the bands in solution spectra are at lower energy. It is quite probable that there is a distortion of the octahedron in solution as the two nitrogen ligands are in transposition. Hence the complexes have presumably a spin-free octahedral configuration on the basis of their analysis, magnetic moments and electronic spectral data.

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Mercury Complexes of Sulphonamides

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Manuscript received 14 October 1976, revised 22 February
1977, accepted 27 April 1977

MISRA *et al*¹⁻³ and Shukla *et al*⁴ have reported the cyanoethylation of a large number of sulphonamides. Such cyanoethylated compounds form complexes with mercuric ion with great facility⁵. Recently sulphonamides were used as a complexing agent for various metals⁶ and it was shown by bacteriostatic studies that these complexes are more potent than the parent drugs⁷.

The present communication deals with the study of complexes of some more substituted sulphonamides and cyanoethylated sulphonamides with mercury (II) chloride.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes :

The cyanoethylated sulphanilamides were prepared according to the method of Misra *et al*³.

All the complexes reported were prepared by refluxing a calculated amount of the sulphonamide and mercuric chloride in absolute alcohol. An alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide was added to the

refluxing mixture until the pH remained constant at approx. 8. Refluxing was continued for 2-3 hr. The product obtained was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The quantitative estimation of mercury, chlorine and sulphur was done by the usual methods, viz., mercury volumetrically by titration with thiocyanate⁸, chlorine gravimetrically as AgCl and sulphur gravimetrically as BaSO₄. Conductivity measurements were carried out in nitrobenzene with a conductivity bridge (Philips). Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Grating Infrared Spectrophotometer (Model-177). The results of the chemical analysis are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were quite stable and were found to be insoluble in most of the common organic solvents, viz., benzene, diethyl ether, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and acetone. They are sparingly soluble in nitrobenzene. The analytical results reveal that the ligand and metal are in equimolecular ratio (1 : 1). The low molar conductance shows that these complexes are non-electrolytic in nature⁹. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes shows that the halogen atoms are also bonded to mercury with its inner coordination sphere. This gives coordination number four in all the complexes.

The infrared spectra of the ligand as well as their complexes have been examined. Only the important sites in the sulphanilamide and cyanoethylated sulphanilamide, viz., —NH— and —C≡N groups have been taken into account.

—NH— of the sulphanilamide has two sharp bands at 3380 and 3480 cm⁻¹ owing to the symmetric and N—H stretching vibrations. These bands of —NH— group shift to a lower frequency region in the complexes. As both the —NH₂ groups in the sulphanilamide molecule have a lone pair of electrons, it may be concluded the two NH₂ groups are attached to the two mercury giving a dimeric species, which also explains the insolubility of the complex. A tentative structure of the complex is given in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1